

Rhetorical components in foreign language instruction

Doniyor Ergashev

Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and
Agricultural Mechanization Engineers

National Research University

English language department

teacher

Abstract: The essay discusses the challenges associated with the function of delivery in education, the rhetorical elements of speech culture, the history of speech, the significance of speech in the modern day, and the speech patterns of emerging learners. In this essay, the author presents an analysis of the recommendations and studies made by scientists who study the function of delivery in education.

Keywords: morphological principles, syntactic principles, linguistics, grammar, speech culture, oratory art, elocution, rhetoric, speech, and pronunciation standards.

The capacity to speak and read in a formal setting while maintaining proper synchronic linguistics, pronunciation, and diction is known as elocution. When a teacher delivers instruction with confidence, pupils will develop their speaking skills and conquer any performance anxiety they may require. They have to start with the basics when it comes to instruction delivery to achieve this level. Even if the student is a skilled orator, he may make blunders in synchronic linguistics and pronunciation when speaking in front of an audience. By providing the pupil with the basics, he or she will teach several advanced delivery strategies. One of the current issues with modern linguistics is elocution. The solution to the present problem is explained in terms of our shared progress, although with the strengthening of educational institutions. It should be mentioned that educational institutions are the main source

of inspiration for today's speech culture. The speech culture of this language is a manifestation of particular folklore. Because of the sensitivity of speech, the rhetorical component of speech culture is examined in conjunction with the study of the theory of neglect within the context of linguistic occurrences. Amazing speech is a quality that could catch the auditor's attention and pique the interest of the learner as a result. When speech culture is involved, it's considered a learning aspect of the process and techniques for providing accurate and pertinent speech to the audience once spoken and colloquial language use is understandable.

Elocution is the art of speech produced by a writer or speaker; it is not just a language growth but also a development of grandeur and spirituality. Thus, the purpose of the statement is to give the auditor and consequently the reader a precise impression after delivery is purported.

As a result, specific requirements are made for the delivery. These needs are efficient, free, attractive, logically true, and transparent. These characters are said to have the most delivery choices. The discourse is obvious since it adheres to literary language norms. The following guidelines are considered.

a) Pronunciation standards include how words, sounds, abbreviations, names of individuals, combined verbs, word combinations, morphological indications, and suffix pronunciations should all be done.

b) Principles of morphology: The literary language's morphological rules set it apart from the dialect and scheme. The expression of numerical notions, the shape of words, the verbs of words, and the word itself all exhibit this in literary language.

v) Syntactic principles: how the sentence's subject and predicate relate to one another and how its secondary elements are connected.

g) Orthographic rules: The individual and universal writing rules form the foundation of the literary language. Grammar rules that have been particularly

designed and agreed upon reflect these ideas. All users of this linguistic book must adopt literary language spelling when writing. The foundation of the literary language is composed of grammatical rules and orthographic principles.

d) Linguistic principles: The richness of each language is sufficient for the people who speak it.

In the classroom, elocution is crucial. Teachers frequently utilize elocution in their lessons because of this. Information on individuals, events, and events is crucial to give pupils. There is a direct sound component to teaching; teachers should speak in an attractive, strong voice that draws students in. The instructor must be aware of his voice's power in order to do this. It's no secret that using proper and clear communication is essential to teaching success compared to other professions. To maintain the perception of a flawless and important educator in the eyes of his students, a professional educator should always be mindful of the phonetic aspects of his speech. During class, some professors frequently talk louder than they do outside of it. They appear to "press" the classroom noise in this way. Although this method's effect is not as significant, it is fast enough and does not require the teacher's audio equipment. Some instructors use hushed tones when teaching. In addition, the instructor feels under pressure since he is unable to produce meaningful outcomes and loses the reader's interest.

References:

1. Pasechnaya I.N. Culture of speech (aspects of the generation of utterance). - 2012. - P. 9-28.
2. Gabunia Z., Bashieva S. Rhetoric as part of traditional culture. - Nalchik, ELPHA, 1993. - P. 3-77.
3. World Book Encyclopedia. – USA: World Book, 1994. V.14. – P. 819.
4. Махкамова Г.Т. Проектирование учебно-методических комплексов в магистратуре. – Т.: Tafakkur qanoti, 2012.

